

Physico Chemical Studies of Pr(III) and Nd(III)-Malonate Complexes

L. L. SONI

Chemistry Department, Maulana Azad College of Technology, Bhopal-7

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Stoichiometry (1 : 1) of Pr(III) and Nd(III)-Malonate complexes have been studied by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method using conductivity and pH-ratio titration methods. Stability constants of complexes at pH 3.0 to 4.5 have been evaluated from Job's curve using non-equimolar solution at $27 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and found to be 4.2 and 4.6 for Pr and Nd respectively and by Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method at three different temperatures and an ionic strength of 0.1μ in 1.0 M KCl. Stability constant obtained in aqueous medium at 30° , 35° , 40° is 4.46, 4.60, 4.82 for Pr and 4.52, 4.68, 4.95 for Nd.

Complexes of some bivalent and trivalent metal ions with malonic acid have been investigated by different group of workers. But in rare-earth elements work has been reported only on La and Gd¹. Therefore in this paper detailed study of the stoichiometric ratio and stability constants have been made.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

Approximately $0.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ solution of Malonic acid (G.R.E. Merck) was prepared in doubly distilled water. Praseodymium and Neodymium salt solution were prepared as mentioned in the previous paper².

Conductometric measurements were made on W.T.W. (Magic eye type) L.B.R. conductivity bridge with dip type cell. Cambridge pH-meter with an accuracy of 0.01 units

was used for pH-measurements after proper calibration with standard buffers. Temperature is kept constant $\pm 0.1^\circ$ using neo-thermostat.

Job's method of continuous variation³, mole ratio method⁴ for conductometry and pH ratio titration method were used for the stoichiometry of the complexes as 1 : 1 (M.L.).

Stability Constants :

(A) *Job's Method* : By using non-equimolar solutions ($M/200$ and $M/250$) method of Job, value of $\log K$ for Pr and Nd obtained at $27^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ is 4.2 and 4.6 respectively.

(B) *pH titration method using Calvin-Bjerrum's technique*⁵ : Following sets were prepared :

- (1) 10 ml of 0.04M malonic acid + 5.0 ml of 0.1M HCl + 1.302 ml of 1.0M KCl + 13.298 ml of water.
- (2) 10.0 ml of 0.04M malonic acid + 5.0 ml of 0.1M HCl + 10.0 ml of 0.004M (Pr. or Nd.-chloride) + 1.062 ml of 1.0M KCl + 3.938 ml of water.

Jobs Method For Composition

pH titrations were carried out with 0.1M sodium-hydroxide in an oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere and at a constant ionic strength of 0.1μ in 1.0M KCl. \bar{n} values were evaluated from the horizontal distance between the reference curve and the curve obtained in presence of metal ion. Formation curve is obtained by plotting \bar{n} values against pA ($-\log A$) and the value of stability constant was found out at $\bar{n} = 0.5$. Above experiment is repeated at 30° , 35° , and 40° . $\log K$ values found are : 4.46, 4.60, 4.82 and 4.52, 4.68, 4.95 for Pr and Nd respectively.

Malonic acid is a di-carboxylic acid and the stability constant obtained shows that this is a moderately stable complex. Following probable structure is proposed for the complexes :

where M stands for Pr or Nd ion.

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REFERENCES

1. Sinha, and P. C. Shyama, "Complexes of Rare-earths"
2. L. L. Soni and G. Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 799.
3. P. Job, *Ann. Chimie.*, 1928 (X), **9**, 113; 1938 (XI), **6**, 97.
4. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
5. M. Calvin and Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.

